

Influence of *Ortho* Substituents on Intramolecular Hydrogen Bonding

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Ultraviolet absorption spectra of some substituted *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols in ethanol and in cyclohexane are recorded and analysed with a view to finding the influence of *ortho* substituents on intramolecular hydrogen bonding. A methyl group, *ortho* to $-OH$, is seen to have no significant effect on the hydrogen bond, but a methyl group, *ortho* to $-NO_2$, renders the hydrogen bond very weak, though hydrogen-bond formation is not prevented.

When two *ortho* substituents in a benzene ring are involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding, the stability of the hydrogen bond depends on its coplanarity with the benzene ring. Hunter¹ has given examples in which intramolecular hydrogen bonding is either disturbed or prevented by steric interference of adjacent substituents. We have examined how hydrogen bonding in *o*-nitrophenol would be affected by the introduction of a methyl group, *ortho* to $-OH$ (I) or to $-NO_2$ (II).

(I)

(II)

It is possible to detect intramolecular hydrogen bonding in phenols by means of ultraviolet absorption spectra. Burawoy *et al.*² in extending an earlier study of Morton and Stubbs³ have found that in absence of internal hydrogen bonding in phenols and intramolecular steric effects in their methyl ethers, phenols absorb in a non-polar solvent like hexane at shorter wave lengths, but in ethanol at longer wave lengths than the corresponding methyl ethers. They also found that a change in the dielectric constant of the solvent did not have much effect on the absorption characteristics of chelated phenols. Employing the above criteria for the presence of an internal hydrogen bond, Baliah and Aleykutty⁴ showed the existence of chelation in *o*-hydroxysulphones. The same criteria are employed for detecting intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the present study.

In order to decide whether there is chelation or not in 2-methyl-6-nitrophenol, it is desirable to examine the effect of solvent as well as the effect of methylation on the

1. "The Stereochemistry of the Hydrogen Bond" in "Progress in Stereochemistry", Ed: Klyne, Butterworths Publications Ltd., London, 1954, pp. 232-234.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2310, 3734, 4703; 1955, 3727.
3. *Ibid.*, 1940, 1347.
4. *This Journal*, 1957, 34, 364.

spectra of the above compound and of its isomer, 2-methyl-4-nitrophenol. The data obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

	Cyclohexane.		Ethanol (95%).	
	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.
2-Methyl-6-nitrophenol	347-360 m μ	3,400	348-361 m μ	2,800
	280	8,150	285	6,900
2-Methyl-6-nitroanisole	251-255	3,850	256-260	3,800
2-Methyl-4-nitrophenol	294	9,000	416-417	3,600
	228	9,500	318-328	8,600
2-Methyl-4-nitroanisole	302	9,850	232	6,450
	229	10,200	312-318	10,000
			230	7,700

Benzene exhibits three bands at about 260, 200, and 180 m μ . The bands at 260 and 200 m μ are referred to as secondary and primary bands respectively⁵. The 260 m μ band is also called B-band⁶. For benzene, the molecular extinction coefficients at 260 and 200 m μ are 230 and 8000 respectively⁷. The transition at 260 m μ ($A_{1g} \rightarrow B_{2u}$) is forbidden and therefore weak. Substitution perturbs the benzene ring by the mesomeric as well as the inductive effects. The mesomeric effect seems to cause a greater perturbation. Atoms containing lone pairs of electrons, when attached to the benzene ring, cause a bathochromic shift of the 260 m μ band and intensify it. The greater the polarisability of the attached atom, the greater is the intensity of the band. The inductive effect has relatively much less influence on the B-band. This may be seen from the spectra of anilinium ion, methylphenylsulphone, and similar compounds.

The primary (200 m μ) band of benzene is much more affected by the inductive effect. It undergoes a bathochromic shift and increases in intensity when groups causing inductive and mesomeric effects are attached to the benzene nucleus.

Analysis of the Spectra obtained in Cyclohexane Solution

2-Methyl-6-nitrophenol and 2-methyl-4-nitrophenol exhibit two absorption bands (Figs. 1 and 2). The two bands of the *o*-nitrophenol do not seem to correspond to the two bands of the *p*-nitrophenol. The 347-360 m μ band of the *o*-nitrophenol corresponds to the secondary band of benzene displaced towards longer wave lengths by the introduction of the hydroxyl and nitro groups (intramolecular hydrogen bond also seems to contribute to this bathochromic shift); the 280 m μ band corresponds to the principal absorption band ($\lambda_{\max}$ 253 m μ ; $\epsilon_{\max}$ 9900 in cyclohexane) of nitrobenzene and it is presumably the primary band of benzene shifted to longer wave lengths by the nitro group. The *p*-nitrophenol has a band at 294 m μ corresponding to the 280 m μ band of its *ortho*-

5. Doub and Vandenberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 714.

6. Braude, *Ann. Reports*, 1945, **42**, 105.

7. Gillam and Stern, "Electronic Absorption Spectroscopy", Edward Arnold, London, 1955, p. 119.

isomer. The absorption occurring at a longer wave length for the *p*-nitrophenol can be explained from the fact that it has a longer conjugated system in the excited state.

FIG. 1

Methylation of the *p*-nitrophenol has caused a shift of the 294 $m\mu$ band to longer wave lengths with increase in intensity. This is the normal effect of methylation in agreement with the greater electron-repelling power of the methyl group. On the other hand, methylation of the *o*-nitrophenol has caused the disappearance of the longer wave length band, the other band undergoing a hypsochromic shift. These spectral changes are a consequence of the steric inhibition of the mesomeric effect of the methoxyl and nitro groups.

Analysis of the Spectra obtained in Ethanol Solution

The following are the outstanding features: The spectrum of 2-methyl-6-nitrophenol in ethanol is essentially the same as that in cyclohexane (Fig. 1). This is an important characteristic of a strongly chelated phenol. The persistence of chelation prevents inter-

molecular hydrogen-bond formation with the solvent and the solvent effect becomes negligible. 2-Methyl-4-nitrophenol behaves differently. It forms hydrogen bond with the solvent and the spectrum in ethanol (especially in the longer wave length region) is strikingly different from that in cyclohexane (Fig. 2). The methyl ethers of both the *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols, on the other hand, show no significant solvent effect.

FIG. 2

The similarity of spectra in cyclohexane and in ethanol for a chelated phenol and the dissimilarity of such spectra for an unchelated phenol may indeed be used as a criterion of chelation in a phenol. Fig. 3 illustrates the spectra of some more chelated and less chelated phenols.

Having established that there exists chelation in 2-methyl-6-nitrophenol, it would be of interest to know whether there exists chelation or not in 3,5-dimethyl-2-nitrophenol (II), in which the nitro group is subjected to a steric effect.

The spectral data obtained with 3,5-dimethyl-2-nitrophenol, 3,5-dimethyl-4-nitrophenol (IV), and their methyl ethers are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

	Cyclohexane.		Ethanol (95%).	
	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.
3,5-Dimethyl-2-nitrophenol	357 $m\mu$	3,600	271-273 $m\mu$	2,400
	290	8,000	241-242	2,500
			217	2,500
3,5-Dimethyl-2-nitroanisole	265-280	1,800	265-269	1,500
			244-249	1,700
3,5-Dimethyl-4-nitrophenol	335-350	800	347-360	1,600
	272	3,100	281	2,700
			249	3,500
2,5-Dimethyl-4-nitroanisole	273	4,100	345-355	1,200
			279	2,600
			249	2,700

The following are the chief spectral features of the compounds listed in Table II.

FIG. 4

3,5-Dimethyl-2-nitrophenol exhibits the primary band at 290 $m\mu$ and the secondary band in the 350-370 $m\mu$ region (Fig. 4). The spectrum is very much like that of

2-methyl-6-nitrophenol. The spectrum in ethanol is not, however, quite similar to that in cyclohexane. Both the primary and secondary bands have undergone a hypsochromic effect in ethanol. If chelation is strong, the spectra in the two solvents should almost be identical. The observed spectral behaviour suggests that chelation in 3,5-dimethyl-2-nitrophenol is weak and that it breaks in a polar solvent like ethanol, giving rise to new spectral effects. There is presumably intermolecular hydrogen-bond formation with the solvent.

3,5-Dimethyl-4-nitrophenol and its methyl ether exhibit the usual spectral characteristics expected of them (Fig. 5). Here we should take into consideration the fact that the nitro group is flanked on either side by methyl groups.

FIG. 5

We thus find that there exists strong chelation in 2-methyl-6-nitrophenol. A methyl group, *ortho* to -OH, does not significantly affect the chelating power of the -OH group. We also find that there is chelation in 3,5-dimethyl-2-nitrophenol, but chelation in this case is weak. It is destroyed in a solvent which can form intermolecular hydrogen bond.

It is also of interest to examine the primary band of 3,5-dimethyl-2-nitrophenol in cyclohexane and in ethanol. In cyclohexane, effective conjugation of the HO- and -NO₂

groups through the benzene ring is indicated by the longer wave length and high intensity of the band. Chelation makes this conjugation possible, perhaps forcing the adjacent methyl group out of the plane of the benzene ring. In ethanol, no conjugation is indicated. On the other hand, the band is even weaker than that of nitrobenzene ($C_6H_5NO_2$ in C_2H_5OH : λ_{max} 259 $m\mu$; ϵ_{max} 8,250). This indicates that rupture of chelation leads to the NO_2 group being forced out of the plane of the benzene ring.

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